

AN UNCOMMON COMPLICATION OF A COMMON PROCEDURE: ABERRANT PLACEMENT OF A CATHETER INTO THE URETER FOLLOWING SUPRAPUBIC CYSTOSTOMY

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ABSTRACT A 70-year-old man was admitted with fever and urinary retention. A suprapubic catheter (SPC) was placed following failed attempts to catheterise due to urethral stricture. The patient subsequently improved and a micturating cystourethrogram (MCUG) was arranged to assess his stricture. Upon injection of contrast via his SPC at the time of MCUG, it was noted the catheter had been inadvertently placed, and the balloon dilated in the proximal third of the patient's right ureter. The balloon was deflated and the catheter repositioned. An intravenous urogram done four weeks following repositioning of his catheter showed no adverse sequelae with a patent ureter and no hydronephrosis on the affected side.

KEYWORDS Suprapubic cystostomy, malposition

INTRODUCTION

Suprapubic cystostomy is a commonly performed urological procedure. It is generally safe and straightforward without many of the long-term complications of urethral catheters [1]. However, as with all surgical procedures, complications are possible. One exceedingly rare complication is obstruction of the ureter by the catheter, and this is most commonly seen in patients with long-term catheters [2]. We describe an occurrence which is rarer still – inadvertent ureteric placement of a suprapubic catheter in a patient presenting with acute urinary retention.

CASE REPORT

A 70-year-old Caucasian male was admitted to the hospital with complaints of fever and generally feeling unwell over the preced-

ing few days. He also gave a history of progressively worsening lower urinary tract symptoms over the last six months – hesitancy, weak stream and incomplete emptying. On admission, he was febrile and looked unwell. Examination of his abdomen revealed a palpable bladder. His serum inflammatory markers were deranged, but his renal indices were within normal limits. His WBC was 15,000/uL, and serum creatinine was 70 umol/L. He was commenced on intravenous antibiotics and passage of a urethral catheter was attempted but failed. Following unsuccessful attempts at catheterization by the on-call urologist, flexible cystoscopy and passage of a guidewire was attempted but also failed due to an impassable bulbar stricture. The patient then underwent suprapubic cystostomy utilizing the Seldinger technique to position a 16 Ch silicone catheter over a guidewire (S-Cath System, MediPlus). The procedure, which was not done under ultrasound guidance due to an distended bladder and the absence of a midline scar, was uneventful and 6mls of water were left in the catheter balloon. The patient recovered well, with improvement in his clinical and laboratory parameters. His catheter continued to drain well, and he was discharged from the hospital with plans to conduct a micturating cystourethrogram (MCUG). At the time of the MCUG, four weeks later, it was noted that the catheter was draining well, but he complained of slight right flank pain. Injection of contrast

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Figure 1: Position of the catheter in the right ureter with an inflated balloon (red arrow).

Figure 2: Reflux of contrast up the right ureter on MCUG. Note the focal dilation of the ureter created by the catheter balloon.

Figure 3: Bulbar stricture is demonstrated on MCUG.

Figure 4: Four-week intravenous urogram. There is no hydronephrosis on the affected side and complete resolution of the focal dilation caused by the balloon

through the suprapubic catheter revealed that the suprapubic catheter was mispositioned in his right ureter with resultant hydronephrosis (Fig. 1). The catheter was deflated and repositioned in his bladder, and an MCUG was performed. There was contrast reflux up his right ureter with mild hydronephrosis but no contrast extravasation (Fig. 2). His bladder was grossly trabeculated with multiple diverticula, and it was noted that he had a tight bulbar urethral stricture (Fig. 3). The patient was imaged with an intravenous urogram four weeks following the repositioning of the SPC – this showed good excretion from both renal units with no evidence of obstruction on the affected side (Fig. 4). He has been listed for surgical management of the stricture.

DISCUSSION

Inadvertent placement is a rare complication of urinary catheterisation. Among these cases, aberrant placement of a suprapubic catheter is even less common. In a literature review by Luo et al. [2], among 20 cases of mispositioned catheters, 16 were as a result of indwelling urethral catheters, and four were suprapubic. In this review, most were long-term catheters for neurogenic bladder, and there was a male to female ratio of 1:3. Taken together, this highlights the novelty of our patient – primary placement of an SPC in a patient with acute urinary retention.

In our patient, the ureteric passage of the catheter was likely facilitated by vesicoureteral reflux (VUR) and a wide ureteric orifice as a result of chronic outlet obstruction. As mentioned above, most reported cases of aberrant placement of a catheter into the ureter have been in patients with a long-term catheter as a result of neurogenic bladder, and it has been theorised that this is the result of a contracted bladder, reduced in volume and with VUR [3].

Among patients in whom the mispositioning has occurred on the first insertion, pain has been described as an early fea-

ture, usually on inflation of the balloon. One exception to this is the neurogenic patient in whom pain may not be pronounced. Other potential clues to a catheter mispositioned in the ureter include resistance on inflation on the bulb as well as flank pain on flushing the catheter [2]. An unexpectedly short external section of the catheter may be another warning sign. Patients may also present with pain as a result of ureteric rupture or with an infection on the affected side [4, 5, 6]. Our patient, surprisingly did not complain of pain on initial placement of the tube and complained of only minor discomfort following placement and was only discovered upon evaluation of his stricture disease. It was fortunate that the catheter was not inflated to maximum capacity but was, as is the author's practice, inflated just enough keep it in situ (5-6mls) – this may have prevented ureteric rupture. Although the catheter was mispositioned, it continued to drain well with no recurrence of his retention. This was likely due to VUR with the flow of urine around the catheter, even from the contralateral renal unit.

The clinical picture dictates management of the patient with a catheter mispositioned in the ureter. This may be just simply removing or repositioning the catheter as in our patient or may involve placement of a stent or nephrostomy tube [5, 7] and even surgical repair in the case of a severely injured ureter [6, 8]. These patients are at risk of ureteral strictures and should be monitored with upper tract imaging [2]. We elected not to place a nephrostomy at the time of discovery of the mispositioned balloon given that the patient was well and asymptomatic. However, we did arrange, as documented, follow up upper tract imaging to ensure ureteric patency and in the interim, the patient was warned to return to hospital if he developed flank pain or fever.

Concerning prevention, one should be aware of this complication and particular subgroups who may be at risk. Luo et al. [2] recommend the use of short tipped catheters and, if available, bedside ultrasonography to ensure correct placement of the catheter balloon in the bladder.

CONCLUSION

Aberrant placement of a suprapubic catheter into the ureter is a rare complication of a standard procedure. Awareness is key especially in patients who are at risk. If in doubt, ultrasonography or CT scan should be considered to ensure that the catheter balloon is indeed in the bladder.

PATIENT CONSENT

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case report and any accompanying images. A copy of the written consent is available for review by the Editor-in-Chief of this journal.

COMPETING INTERESTS

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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